

Litany for Priests (Author Unknown)

Priests who are alone: accompany them, Lord.

Missionary priests: protect them, Lord.

Priests who are preachers: enlighten them, Lord.

Priest who direct souls: instruct them, Lord.

Priests and religious who have died: bring them to glory,
Lord.

For all priests: give them Your wisdom and knowledge.

For all priests: give them Your understanding and counsel.

For all priests: give them reverence and awe of You.

For all priests: give them patience and love.

For all priests: give them obedience and kindness.

For all priests: give them a burning zeal for souls.

For all priests: give them virtues of faith, hope and love.

For all priests: give them an intense love for the Eucharist.

For all priests: give them loyalty to the Holy Father and
their Bishops.

For all priests: give them respect for life and human dig-
nity.

For all priests: give them integrity and justice.

For all priests: give them humility and generosity.

For all priests: give them strength in their labors.

For all priests: give them peace in their sufferings.
For all priests: give them great love for the Trinity.
For all priests: give them great love for Mary.
For all priests: let them be the light of Christ.
For all priests: let them be the salt of the earth.
For all priests: let them practice sacrifice and self-denial.
For all priests: let them be holy in body, mind and spirit.
For all priests: let them be men of prayer.
For all priests: may faith shine forth in them.
For all priests: may they be concerned for our salvation.
For all priests: may they be faithful to their priestly vocation.
For all priests: may their hands bless and heal.
For all priests: may they burn with love for you.
For all priests: may all their steps be for the glory of God.
For all priests: may the Holy Spirit fill them, and give them His gifts in abundance.

Anonymous